

Sample 21a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0139
{Si}	47.9
{Al, Si}	12.7
{Fe}	8.8
{Si, Ca LoP}	8.0
{Ca}	5.2
{Si, Ca HiP}	3.3
{Al, Si, Ca}	2.6
{Si, Fe}	1.8
{Na, Al, Si}	1.7
{Al, Si, K}	1.6
{Al}	1.1
{Mg, Si}	0.9
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
{Si, K}	0.3
{Na, Si}	0.3
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.3
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
{Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Al, Ca}	0.2
{Zn-LA1}	0.2
{Si, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, Ca}	0.1
{Ti}	0.1
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Al, Fe}	0.1
{S, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
{P, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Cl}	0.0
{Al, Si, Ti}	0.0
{Mg, Fe}	0.0
{Al, Si, S}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.8
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.7
BOF converter slag	1.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.9
Desulph slag	1.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Olivine flux	0.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.4
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	14.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.1
Carbon rich - other	1.0
Cement or BOF converter	5.3
Cement	7.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.2
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	44.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	11.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.6
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.4
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	6.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.7
Site - slag	3.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.4
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	14.3
Site - carbon-rich other	1.1
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.0
Urban; rarely site - slag	5.3
Urban	8.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	44.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	11.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.7
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 21b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0750
	{Si}	50.4
	{Al, Si}	10.8
	{Fe}	8.8
	{Si, Ca LoP}	7.5
	{Ca}	5.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	2.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	2.2
	{Al, Si, K}	1.9
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Si, Fe}	1.5
	{Al}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.6
Pellet	2.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.6
BOF converter slag	2.6
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.9
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.3
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.3
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	6.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	1.8
Cement or BOF converter	6.4
Cement	9.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	47.3
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	13.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.2
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	7.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.6
Site - slag	3.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.3
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.4
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	6.4
Urban	9.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	47.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	13.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 21c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.2436
	{Si}	45.7
	{Al, Si}	13.3
	{Fe}	7.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	5.7
	{Mg, Al, Si}	3.9
	{Ca}	3.5
	{Al}	3.1
	{Si, Ca HiP}	2.4
	{Al, Si, K}	2.0
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.7
	{Al, S}	1.6
	{Si, Fe}	1.4
	{S}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{Ca, Fe}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, S}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	2.2
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	0.9
BOF converter slag	2.2
BOF converter slag slopping	0.6
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	7.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.0
Carbon rich - other	1.0
Cement or BOF converter	4.1
Cement	5.7
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	3.9
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	52.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	11.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.2
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.5
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	7.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.9
Site - slag	3.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.6
Site - carbon-rich other	1.0
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	4.1
Urban	9.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	52.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	11.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.2
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels